

Studies on alkylation of Hagemann's ester and its derivatives with alkyl halides and Michael acceptors[†]

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Alkylation and Michael addition of ethyl 3-methyl-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohex-2-enecarboxylate (**1b**) have been studied under basic conditions. Similar reactions with Hagemann's ester (**1c**) have been carried out using phase transfer catalysts as well as solid supports. The ratio of the C-1 to C-3 alkylated products have been determined. A probable explanation for the regioselectivity observed has been given.

Alkylation study of cyclic vinylogous β -ketoester system described earlier convincingly demonstrated that in system of the type (**1**) possessing two reactive centres at 1 and 3, the course of reaction is largely dependent on the nature of R^{1-3} , the nature of the alkylating agent³ and to some extent on the experimental conditions used³. Alkylation and Michael addition of Hagemann's ester (ethyl 3-methyl-4-oxocyclohex-2-enecarboxylate) (**1c**) have been studied under basic conditions by Nasipuri *et al.*⁴. A quantitative analysis of the product ratio (C-1 : C-3) was performed by using GLC and NMR spectroscopy as analytical tools. They obtained a higher ratio of the C-1 alkyl esters with Michael addition reactions. This has been rationalised on the basis of steric and electronic factors in the transition states. More work along these lines with such system (**1**) was therefore warranted in order to fully evaluate the nature of the influence exerted by the substituent R_1 and in order to rationalise the observed regioselectivity of different alkylating agents with a change of the base from different base-solvent combinations to phase transfer catalysts and supported reagents. This paper deals with the synthesis and reactions of ethyl 3-methyl-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohex-2-enecarboxylate (**1b**) and the study of alkylation of Hagemann's ester (**1c**) in presence of phase transfer catalysts (PTC) and supported reagents.

Results and Discussion

The synthesis of **1b** was carried out starting from ethyl benzoylacetate which on reaction with the methiodide of the Mannich base, 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one⁵ in presence of sodium ethoxide resulted in a mixture from which the aldol ethyl 2-hydroxy-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohexanecarboxylate was isolated. Dehydration with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid yielded the unsaturated ketoester (**1a**) which on treatment with methyl iodide furnished ethyl 3-methyl-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohex-2-enecarboxylate (**1b**) in excellent yield.

The reaction of **1b** with methyl iodide and benzyl bromide in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide afforded a mixture of C-1 (**2b**) and C-3 (**3b**) alkylated products. Since separation of the isomeric products could not be easily achieved, and estimation of the product ratio from NMR⁴ spectral studies was not helpful in this case, the procedure of Mukharji¹ for assessing the relative amounts of the two isomers was adopted. The condensation products in each case were hydrolysed with dilute potassium hydroxide solution whereby the isomer **3b** was converted to the corresponding acid and the isomer **2b** gave the neutral ketone. From the relative amounts of the acid and ketone formed it was obvious that in the mixture initially formed, the isomer **3b** constituted the principal product which meant that C-3 alkylation had occurred predominantly. This result was in harmony with that obtained by Mukharji¹ and Nasipuri *et al.*⁴.

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Reaction of **1b** with methyl vinyl ketone (MVK) under similar conditions followed by alkali hydrolysis afforded **4** as the major product together with a minor amount of a neutral ketone which was found to be identical with that obtained from the alkali hydrolysis of **1b**. Compound **4** must have formed through the addition of MVK next to the keto group in **1b** to give the intermediate **3b** ($R = CH_2CH_2COCH_3$), which being a 1,5-diketone readily underwent cyclisation and subsequent hydrolysis. Thus, it is evident that the condensation of **1b** with MVK occurred at C-3. The compound corresponding to the addition of MVK at C-1 of **1b** could not however be isolated. This result appears to be contradictory to that reported by Mukharji¹. Thus the result cannot be solely explained on the basis of electronic factors as suggested by the earlier workers since then both furyl and phenyl analogues would have shown at least qualitatively similar selectivity.

Alkylation of **1** using base-solvent combination has been reported in the literature¹⁻⁷. Michael reaction and regioselective alkylation of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and β -substituted enones have also been carried out on the surface of alumina and silica^{8,9}. Since there is no report on alkylation of **1c** in presence of PTC and supported reagents alkylation of **1c** was carried out under the above conditions with a view to obtaining regioselective products.

Reaction of **1c** with ethyl iodide, isopropyl iodide and benzyl chloride in presence of benzyltriethylammonium chloride and with benzyl chloride in presence of tetrabutylammonium iodide as well as tetrabutylammonium bromide yielded a mixture of C-1 and C-3 alkylated products which contain the C-3 adduct in major proportion. Also, the ratio of C-3 product was seen to increase with the increase in size of the alkyl groups (Table 1). However, with Michael acceptors such as methyl acrylate and ethyl cyanoacrylate the C-1 alkylated product occurred predominantly along with an appreciable amount of the dialkylated product.

Table 1

PTC ^a	Alkylating agent	Temp. °C	Time h	Ratio of 2c : 3c
BTEAC	C ₂ H ₅ I	65-70	8	35 : 65
BTEAC	PrI	65-70	8	25 : 75
BTEAC	PhCH ₂ Cl	65-70	6	20 : 80
TBAI	PhCH ₂ Cl	65-70	6	15 : 85
TBAB	PhCH ₂ Cl	65-70	6	15 : 85
BTEAC	CH ₂ =CHCO ₂ Me	45-50	5	100 : 0 ^b
BTEAC	CH ₂ =CHCN	room temp.	3	100 : 0 ^b

^aBTEAC = benzyltriethylammonium chloride, TBAI = tetrabutylammonium iodide, TBAB = tetrabutylammonium bromide.

^bAppreciable amount of dialkylated product was obtained.

A plausible explanation may be as follows. Of the two anionic centres C-1 and C-3, the bulky positive part of the PTC forms a tight complex with the less crowded anion at C-1. This facilitates attack of the alkyl group at C-3 resulting in the formation of C-3 alkylated product in major yield. The fact that the amount of the C-3 product increases with increase in size of the alkylating agent supports the above explanation. In case of Michael addition only the C-1 adduct could be characterised from NMR spectral data. The presence of the dialkylated product showed that C-3 alkylation had proceeded to a considerable extent. At this stage no definite conclusion regarding the selectivity of Michael addition could be drawn.

With change of the base from PTC to sodium ethoxide adsorbed on alumina and with the same alkyl halides and Michael acceptors the major product obtained in each case was the C-1 isomer (Table 2). With sodium ethoxide adsorbed on silica no such selectivity was observed.

Table 2

Alkylating agent	Ratio of 2c : 3c
C ₂ H ₅ I	75 : 25
PrI	70 : 30
PhCH ₂ Cl	65 : 35
CH ₂ =CHCO ₂ Me	65 : 35
CH ₂ =CHCN	100 : 0 ^a

^aAppreciable amount of dialkylated product was obtained.

It has been observed that in case of displacement reactions with solid support the proximity of the electrophile and the nucleophile is brought about by the process of chemisorption. On silica gel the electrophilicity of the electrophile increase due to the donation of the H⁺ by the hydrated silicic acid while on solid support such as alumina the nucleophilicity of the nucleophile is enhanced¹⁰ due to the presence of surface hydroxides on alumina. In case of the ambident nucleophile (**1**) due to the presence of methyl at C-2, the C-3 anion is adsorbed on the solid support. This enhances the nucleophilicity of the C-1 anion thus facilitating attack of the electrophile at this site. The same trend was observed in the case of Michael reaction.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. UV spectra (EtOH) were measured on a Carl-Zeiss PM Q 11 spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr/film) on Pye-Unicam SP 200 and Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometers and ¹H NMR spectra on Varian-60A, Varian EM-360 and Varian EM-390 spectrometers with TMS as the internal standard (*J* values recorded in

Hz). Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

Ethyl 2-hydroxy-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohexanecarboxylate : Methyl iodide (16 g, 0.113 mol) was added dropwise to stirred, ice-cooled and freshly distilled 1-diethylaminobutane-3-one (14.3 g, 0.10 mol) [prepared from diethylamine hydrochloride (110 g, 0.1 mol) and paraformaldehyde (42 g, 1.4 mol)] for 1 h and the mixture was further cooled for 30 min before attaining room temperature. The excess methyl iodide was removed under reduced pressure to afford the dry methiodide. Anhydrous benzene (100 ml) was then added followed by ethyl benzoyl acetate (75 g, 0.5 mol) [prepared from ethyl benzoate (75 g, 0.5 mol), sodium (2 g, 0.08 mol) and ethyl acetate (10 ml)] and the mixture was immersed in an ice-bath. Sodium ethoxide [prepared from sodium (2.8 g, 0.12 mol) and super dry EtOH (65 ml)] was added dropwise to the stirred and cooled mixture. Stirring was continued for another hour after which the mixture was acidified with excess acetic acid and diluted with water. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous portion was extracted with ether-benzene mixture. The combined ether-benzene extracts was washed with sodium bicarbonate (10%) to remove the excess acid and finally washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent afforded a solid (14 g, 53%), m.p. 128° (lit.⁷ 128–30°); ν_{\max} 3400 and 1720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.00 (3H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.09–2.55 (4H, m, methylene), 3.40 (1H, t, H-1), 3.90 (2H, q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.10 (1H, s, OH), 7.10–7.40 (5H, m, ArH).

Ethyl 4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohex-2-enecarboxylate (1a) : A mixture of ethyl 2-hydroxy-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohexanecarboxylate (10 g) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (1 g) was heated under reflux for 5 h in a flask fitted with a Dean and Stark water separator. The reaction mixture was then cooled, washed with sodium bicarbonate (10%), water and dried. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure afforded the product (8.6 g, 88%), b.p. 162°/0.9 mm; ν_{\max} 1725 and 1765 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.10 (3H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.10–2.50 (4H, m, methylene), 3.90–4.20 (3H, m, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$, CH), 6.4 (1H, s, vinyl H), 7.20–7.45 (5H, ArH).

Ethyl 3-methyl-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohex-2-enecarboxylate (1b) : Compound **1a** (12.5 g, 0.051 mol) was added dropwise to a stirred ice-cold solution of sodium ethoxide [prepared from sodium (1.18 g, 0.051 mol) and dry EtOH (45 ml)]. The mixture was stirred for 30 min and excess methyl iodide (10 g) was added dropwise. After complete addition it was stirred for 1 h and refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The alcohol and excess methyl iodide were then removed under reduced pressure. Usual work-up afforded an oil (10 g, 76%), b.p. 150–52°/0.5 mm; ν_{\max} 1665 and 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.10 (3H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.72

(3H, s, CH_3), 2.30–2.80 (4H, m, methylene), 3.70 (1H, t, allylic H), 4.00 (2H, q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 7.15–7.40 (5H, m, ArH).

General method of alkylation of ketoester (1b) : The ketoester (**1b**; 2.10 mol) was added to a stirred solution of potassium *t*-butoxide [prepared from potassium (0.21 mol) and dry *t*-butyl alcohol (25 ml)]. After complete addition stirring was continued for 45 min. The alkyl halide (2.50 mol) was then added all at once to the ice-cold potassium salt of the keto ester. The mixture was left over night at room temperature and then refluxed gently on a water-bath for 2 h. The alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue diluted with water and extracted with ether. Usual work-up afforded an oil, which was distilled under reduced pressure to give a pale yellow oil : mixture of compounds **2b** and **3b** ($\text{R} = \text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{Ph}$), b.p. 157–60°/1 mm; mixture of compounds **2b** and **3b** ($\text{R} = \text{CH}_2\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{Ph}$), b.p. 210–15°/3 mm.

General procedure for hydrolysis of the above alkylated mixture : The alkylated products were heated in KOH solution (10%) for 9 h in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and the oily material extracted with ether. Usual work-up followed by removal of the solvent yielded the neutral ketone as an oil which was distilled under reduced pressure : 2,4-dimethyl-3-phenylcyclohex-2-ene-1-one (0.5 g, 12%), b.p. 148–50°/2 mm (Found : C, 8.34; H, 7.82. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires : C, 84.00; H, 8.0%), it gave a deep red crystalline 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 175° (EtOH-EtOAc) (Found : N, 14.46. $\text{C}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires : N, 14.7%); 4-benzyl-2-methyl-3-phenylcyclohex-2-ene-1-one (1 g, 20%), b.p. 148–50°/4 mm; ν_{\max} 1725 and 1620 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.12 (t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.70 (s, CH_3 at C-3), 2.30–2.60 (m, methylene at C-5 and C-6), 2.90 (s, CH_2Ph), 3.60–3.80 (t, allylic H), 4.00 (q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 7.17–7.32 (m, ArH). The above ¹H NMR spectral data reveals the presence of a mixture of the above mentioned compound and **2b** ($\text{R} = \text{CH}_2\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{Ph}$).

The aqueous alkaline portion left after the separation of the above ketone in each case was acidified with acetic acid and extracted with CHCl_3 . Usual work-up afforded a viscous oil which was triturated with EtOAc or chromatographed : 3,3-dimethyl-4-oxo-2-phenyl- $\Delta^{1,2}$ -cyclohexene-1-carboxylic acid : (2.25 g, 54%), m.p. 122° (pet. ether-EtOAc) (Found : C, 7.36; H, 6.32. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 73.77; H, 6.56%); ν_{\max} 1725 and 1705 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.12 (6H, s, CH_3 at C-3), 2.62–2.86 (4H, m, methylene at C-5 and C-6), 6.96–7.30 (5H, m, ArH), 9.50 (1H, s, COOH).

Ethyl ester of the acid prepared by alcohol-sulphuric method was distilled, b.p. 140–42°/0.5 mm (Found : C, 74.73; H, 6.97. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3$ requires : C, 74.99; H, 7.35%); it gave an orange coloured 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 154–55° (EtOH- $CHCl_3$) (Found : N, 12.20. $C_{23}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires : N, 12.33%); it gave a white crystalline semicarbazone derivative, m.p. 155° (EtOH) (Found : N, 12.61. $C_{18}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires : N, 12.76%).

3-Benzyl-4-methyl-4-oxo-2-phenyl- $\Delta^{1,2}$ -cyclohexene-1-carboxylic acid : Chromatography of the oil over silica gel (60 g) afforded a solid in the benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluents, m.p. 157° (EtOAc-pet. ether) (Found : C, 78.48; H, 5.97. $C_{21}H_{20}O_3$ requires : C, 78.5; H, 6.25%); ν_{max} 1720 and 1700 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.06 (3H, s, CH_3 at C-3), 2.30–2.70 (4H, m, methylene at C-5 and C-6), 3.02 (2H, s, CH_2Ph), 7.15–7.36 (10H, m, ArH), 9.32 (1H, s, COOH).

The above keto acid gave a red crystalline 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 218° (EtOH-EtOAc) (Found : N, 11.00. $C_{27}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires : N, 11.26%).

Michael addition of ethyl 3-methyl-4-oxo-2-phenylcyclohex-2-enecarboxylate (1b) to methyl vinyl ketone : A mixture of the keto ester (1b; 10.60 g, 0.04 mol) and freshly distilled methyl vinyl ketone (3.2 g, 0.01 mol) was added to a stirred ice-cooled solution of potassium *t*-butoxide [prepared from potassium (0.36 g, 0.11 mol) and *t*-butanol (20 ml)]. The reaction was performed under nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was kept over night at room temperature, acidified with calculated amount of acetic acid, diluted with water and extracted with ether. Usual work-up followed by the removal of the solvent yielded a viscous liquid (6.3 g), b.p. 190–95°/1 mm.

Hydrolysis of the above Michael reaction product : The above Michael adduct (6.30 g) was refluxed with KOH solution (60 ml; 10%) for 8 h in an atmosphere of nitrogen. It was then cooled and extracted with ether. Usual work-up followed by removal of the solvent yielded a residue which was rehydrolysed with KOH for 7 h and worked up as before to yield a viscous liquid characterised as 2-methyl-3-phenylcyclohex-2-ene-1-one (0.6 g, 6%), b.p. 120°/0.6 mm (Found : C, 83.52; H, 7.32. $C_{13}H_{14}O$ requires : C, 83.87, H, 7.52%); ν_{max} 1665 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.70 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.00–2.80 (6H, m, methylenes), 7.10–7.60 (5H, m, ArH); $[\eta]_D^{28}$ 1.5868.

The above ketone formed a deep red 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 178° (EtOH-EtOAc) (Found : N, 15.12. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4N_4$ requires : N, 15.3%) and a white crystalline semicarbazone derivative, m.p. 210° (EtOH), (Found : N, 16.96. $C_{14}H_{17}ON_3$ requires : N, 17.28%).

6-Carboxy-4,4a,7,8-tetrahydro-4a-methyl-5-phenyl-naphthalene-2(3H)-one : The aqueous alkali portions from the above experiment were acidified with glacial acetic acid and extracted with $CHCl_3$. Removal of the solvent afforded a gummy product which on trituration with EtOAc gave a solid (4 g, 76%), m.p. 196° (Found : C, 76.47; H, 6.26. $C_{18}H_{18}O$ requires : C, 76.56; H, 6.38%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 260 nm (ϵ 7332); ν_{max} 1700 and 1665 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.36 (3H, s, CH_3 at C-4a), 1.60–2.60 (8H, m, methylenes), 5.80 (1H, s, vinyl H), 6.90–7.34 (5H, m, ArH), 9.40 (1H, s, COOH). The above keto acid formed a red crystalline 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 232° (EtOH-EtOAc) (Found : N, 12.00. $C_{24}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires : N, 12.12%).

General procedure for alkylation of 1c with alkyl halide/Michael acceptors in presence of phase transfer catalysts (PTC) : The ester 1c (0.005 mol), alkyl halide/Michael acceptor (0.007 mol), PTC (0.005 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.005 mol) were taken in a mixture of dry benzene (5 ml) and dry DMF (1 ml) and heated while stirring (optimum temperature and time as given in Table 1). The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and extracted with $CHCl_3$. Usual work-up and removal of the solvent afforded a liquid which was distilled under reduced pressure. The ratio of compounds 2c and 3c formed are given in the Table 1 : 2c and 3c (R = C_2H_5 , $R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = H$) (72%), b.p. 150°/4 mm, δ (90 MHz, $CDCl_3$) 0.90 (t, J 6, CH_2CH_3 and $CO_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.28 (m, CH_2CH_3 at C-1 and C-3), 2.00 (bs, CH_3 at C-2), 2.12 (bs, CH_3 at C-2), 2.15–2.50 (m, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 3.20 (t, J 6, H-1), 4.20 (q, J 6, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 6.03 (q, J 1.5, H-3); 2c and 3c (R = Pr^i , $R_1 = Me$, $R_2 = H$) (72%), b.p. 30°/2 mm, δ (60 MHz, CCl_4) 0.96 (d, J 7, $CHMe_2$), 1.10–1.40 (m, $COOCH_2Me$ and CH), 1.90–2.60 (m, CH_2 at C-5 and C-6), 2.00 (s, Me at C-2), 3.20 (t, J 4, H-3), 4.20 (q, J 6, $COOCH_2Me$), 5.80 (q, J 1.5, H-1); 2c and 3c (R = CH_2Ph , $R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = H$) (85%), b.p. 160°/3 mm, δ (90 MHz, $CDCl_3$) 1.25 (t, J 7, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 2.00 (bs, CH_3 at C-2), 2.20 (bs, CH_3 at C-2), 2.25–2.75 (m, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 3.30 (t, J, 5, H-1), 3.70 (bs, CH_2Ph), 4.25 (q, J 5, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 6.03 (q, J 1.5, H-3), 7.20–7.40 (m, ArH); 2c and 3c (R = $CH_2CH_2COOCH_3$, $R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = H$) (73%), b.p. 180°/3 mm, δ (90 MHz, $CDCl_3$) 1.30 (t, J 7, $OCOCH_2CH_3$), 2.00 (s, CH_3 at C-2), 2.10–2.60 (m, $CH_2CH_2COOCH_3$, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 3.65 (s, $OCOCH_3$), 4.2 (q, J 5, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 5.95 (bs, H-3); 2c and 3c (R = CH_2CH_2CN , $R_1 = Me$, $R_2 = H$) (82%), 178°/0.6 mm, δ (60 MHz, CCl_4) 1.30 (t, J 7, $OCOCH_2CH_3$), 2.00 (CH_3 at C-2 and C-3 and CH_2CH_2CN), 2.20–2.40 (m, CH_2 at C-5 and C-6 and CH_2CH_2CN), 4.20 (q, J 7, $OCOCH_2CH_3$), 5.95 (q, J 1.5, H-3).

General procedure for reaction of 1c with alkyl halides and Michael acceptors in presence of sodium ethoxide adsorbed on alumina : Alumina (10 g) was activated at 120° under vacuum for 6 h. To it a solution of sodium ethoxide (0.005 mol) in dry EtOH was added and stirred magnetically for 10 min. The ester 4 (0.005 mol) was then added and stirred again for another 15 min. To it the alkyl halide/Michael acceptor (0.005 mol) was added and stirred for 4 h. The slurry was then eluted from a column with ether. Removal of the solvent afforded an oil containing a mixture of compounds 2c and 3c. The ratio of the compounds is given in Table 2 : 2c and 3c (R = Et, R₁ = Me, R₂ = H) (85%), δ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 0.90 (t, J 7, CH₂CH₃ and COOCH₂CH₂CH₃), 1.50 (m, CH₂CH₃ at C-1 and C-3), 1.90 (bs, Me at C-2), 2.00 (bs, CH₃ at C-2), 2.10–2.60 (m, CH₂ at C-5 and C-6), 3.20 (t, J 4, H-1), 4.20 (q, J 6, COOCH₂CH₃), 5.98 (q, J 15, H-3); 2c and 3c (R = Prⁱ, R₁ = Me, R₂ = H) (88%), δ (60 MHz, CCl₄) 0.85 (d, J 7 CHMe₂), 1.00–1.40 (m, COOCH₂CH₃ and CHMe₂), 1.80–2.60 (m, CH₂ at C-5 and C-6), 1.90 (s, Me at C-2), 3.18 (t, J 4, H-1), 4.18 (q, J 6, COOCH₂Me), 5.85 (q, J 1.5, H-5); 2c and 3c (R = CH₂Ph, R₁ = Me, R₂ = H) (90%), δ (60 MHz, CCl₄) 1.20 (t, J 7, COOCH₂CH₃), 2.00 (bs, Me at C-2), 2.20–2.60 (CH₂ at C-5 and C-6), 3.20 (t, J 5, H-1), 3.70 (bs, CH₂Ph), 4.20 (q, J 6, COOCH₂Me), 5.80 (bs, H-3), 7.10–7.30 (m, ArH); 2c and 3c (R = CH₂CH₂CO₂Me,

R₁ = Me, R₂ = H) (84%), δ (60 MHz, CCl₄) 1.30 (t, J 7, COOCH₂CH₃), 2.00 (s, Me at C-2), 2.10–2.60 (m, CH₂ at C-5 and C-6 and CH₂CH₂COOMe), 3.20 (t, J 5, H-1), 3.65 (s, COOMe), 4.20 (q, J 6, COOCH₂CH₃), 5.80 (q, J 1.5, H-3); 2c and 3c (R = CH₂CH₂CN, R₁ = Me, R₂ = H) (88%), δ (60 MHz, CCl₄) 1.20 (t, J 7, COOCH₂CH₃), 2.00 (bs, Me at C-2 and C-3 and CH₂CHCN), 2.20–2.65 (m, CH₂CH₂CN, CH₂ at C-5 and C-6), 4.20 (q, J 6, COOCH₂CH₃), 5.80 (q, J 1.5, H-3).

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